

Skills 4 eosc

Annex to D2.6 Catalogue of OS career profiles and MVS - update

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Deliverable Abstract

This Annex to D2.6 offers examples of Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) Profiles. Each MVS describes key skills and competences for a role involved in practising Open Science (OS) with the support of the EOOSC. MVS Profiles are synthesised from established competences frameworks and resources. They are proposed as an aid to skills development, especially curriculum and course design. Each MVS Profile relates a skillset to the Open Science (OS) practices, activities, and outcomes that may typically be expected of the role concerned. The methodology is further described in the main D2.6 report.

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¹ As this is the updated version of this catalogue, the original contributions with initial contribution dates are kept. Please see each individual profile for latter adjustments made after internal and external reviews and template updates.

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
v.0.1	8.5.2023	Initial draft based on D2.1 report, community feedback, internally reviewed MVS drafts, and updates as per D2.6	Angus Whyte [lead] and co-authors above
v.1.0	30.6.2023	Draft updated following internal review	As above
v.1.1	24.06.2025	Catalogue collated with updated versions of MVS profiles	Clara Lines Diaz

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS²

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement
DMP	Data Management Plan
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ETHRD IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group (RDA)
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IT	Information Technology
JRC	Joint Research Centre
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
ORCC	Open Research Competencies Coalition
OS	Open Science
R&I	Research and Innovation
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
RI	Research Infrastructure
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RSE	Research Software Engineer
T4fs	Terms for FAIR skills

² See also EOSC Glossary: EOSC Glossary Interest Group. (2020). EOSC Glossary (December 2020). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4472643>.

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Introduction

This Annex to the Skills4EOSC D2.6 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles and Minimum Viable Skillsets: update provides the content of the MVS Profiles for selected roles involved in performing and enabling Open Science.

As described in the main report, the catalogue currently offers the following MVS Profiles:

MVS Title (Role)
Civil Servant
Data Stewards - Coordinator, Embedded
Digital Collections Curator
Ethics Advisor
Knowledge Broker
Legal Expert
Policymaker - Evidence-based policymaker
Policymaker - Research Policy
Researcher - Early Career
Researcher - Senior
Research Infrastructure Professional
Scholarly Communications Professional
Student - Masters Level
Student - Undergraduate

Table 1. Current MVS catalogue entries, with variations

Civil Servant

V0.3 2025

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Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	June 2023	Final draft for D2.1	Emma Lazzeri, Sara di Giorgio, Dominique Green, Claire Sowinski, Gabriela Torres Ramos, Betty Evangelinou, Bojana Koteska
0.2	October 2024	Restructured to add ESCO terms and highlight essential skills	Bojana Koteska
0.3	June 2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential ESCO terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) sets out to describe a shared framework for recognizing the competencies required for civil servants engaged in advancing Open Science. Civil servants are typically employed by Ministers in government departments, where they perform a wide range of administrative, regulatory, or policy-related functions. Civil servants execute the Executive power of the State and play a critical role in ensuring that government operations run smoothly. Although the nature of civil service employment may vary by country and specific role, common positions include clerks, analysts, policy advisors, inspectors, and managers.

Civil servants act as central figures in the execution of government policies and administration. They are responsible for implementing and upholding government regulations, ensuring that public sector bodies operate according to established frameworks and guidelines. Civil servants also play a role in promoting transparency and accountability, particularly in the context of Open Science, by facilitating the appropriate access to and re-use of scientific data for public benefit. They ensure that administrative processes are neutral, non-partisan, and aligned with ethical standards.

One important aspect of civil service employment is that it is typically non-political. Civil servants are expected to remain neutral and non-partisan in their work, ensuring that public sector organizations operate fairly and effectively, free from political bias or favoritism. This neutrality allows them to carry out their duties impartially, maintaining the trust and confidence of the public.

Civil servants create and support open access to scientific knowledge, data, and research results, serving the public interest through the appropriate re-use of data produced and shared by research actions. By embedding Open Science principles into their work, civil servants ensure that the research data generated by various institutions is accessible and reusable, contributing to policy-making, innovation, and public benefit.

In their roles, civil servants uphold Open Science values such as transparency, ethical data use, and accessibility. They act as facilitators in connecting research outcomes with public policy, ensuring that scientific data informs government decisions and serves the public good. Their work supports

evidence-based decision-making and aligns with the mission of promoting Open Science for societal benefit.

Civil Servant

Associated function titles: Civil Servant, Public Policy Advisor, Government Analyst, Administrative Officer, Policy Coordinator, Regulatory Specialist.

Essential Skills for this Role

- Good understanding of OS principles and practices, open data, open research, and open access.
- Developing policies and guidelines that promote OS.
- Solid understanding of OS research ethics
- Being familiar with technology and tools used to support OS practices.
- Managing projects related to OS.
- Providing training and education to researchers, policymakers, and public citizens about OS practices.
- Evaluating the impact of OS practices and making recommendations for future improvement.
- Good understanding of (personal and non-personal) data management, including data storing, analysis, and sharing according to the FAIR and OS principles.
- Good understanding of the regulatory framework (national, regional, and international) concerning intellectual property rights (e.g., copyrights and trade secrets) and other non-personal data (e.g., research data and data held by Public Sector bodies). As an example, in the regional level, this may include, but not be limited to, the Open Data Directive, the Data Governance Act, and the Directives and Regulations concerning Copyrights and Trade Secrets in the EU.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Communication
- Collaboration
- Leadership
- Citizen Engagement
- Negotiation and diplomacy
- Innovative thinking
- Strategic and analytical skills
- Teamwork
- Adaptability to changes

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Clarify and shape OS strategy and priorities for the national and international interest
- Involve and engage the right stakeholders and partners in making recommendations or decisions on OS
- Shape strategies and plans which help put into practice OS (give a long-term direction)
- Develop the capabilities in OS of the staff
- Engage in the open research process
- Ensure compliance with ethical, legal, and regulatory criteria
- Communicate / actively promote OS
- Facilitate the engagement of different stakeholders in co-creation actions

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Research is more transparent, accessible, and reproducible.
- Collaboration and knowledge sharing within the scientific community and beyond.
- Scientific knowledge and research results are openly available, to ensure that taxpayers' money is being used effectively and efficiently, and that the benefits of research are being shared widely.
- Policies that support open access to research publications and data are implemented, encouraging researchers to make their work openly available.
- Collaboration and knowledge-sharing is facilitated between researchers, government agencies, and the public.
- Open science practices are promoted through training and education, and engaging with stakeholders to understand their needs and priorities.
- Decision-making re-uses data that has been produced and shared by research actions.

Further information

Contributors: Emma Lazzeri, Sara di Giorgio, Dominique Green, Claire Sowinski, Gabriela Torres Ramos, Betty Evangelinou, Bojana Koteska

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Manage open publications](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Perform project management](#); [Mentor individuals](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Synthesise information](#); [Manage research data](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#); [Promote the participation of citizens in scientific and research activities](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Participate actively in civic life](#); [Exercise rights and responsibilities](#); [Manage time](#); [Plan](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Address an audience](#); [Build networks](#); [Work in teams](#); [Show initiative](#); [Advise others](#); [Lead others](#); [Make decisions](#); [Motivate others](#); [Show confidence](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Show empathy](#); [Negotiate compromises](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Think creatively](#); [Manage frustration](#); [Approach challenges positively](#); [Think innovatively](#); [Keep an open mind](#); [Think analytically](#); [Solve problems](#); [Build team spirit](#); [Adapt to change](#); [Demonstrate willingness to learn](#).

ResearchComp: [Manage research data](#); [Promote open access publishing](#); [Operate open source software](#); [Mobilise resources](#); [Creativity](#); [Communicate to the broad public](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Teach in academic or vocational contexts](#); [Interact professionally](#); [Interact professionally](#); [Work in teams](#); [Negotiate](#); [Promote citizen science](#); [Creativity](#); [Analytical thinking](#); [Strategic thinking](#).

Terms4FAIRskills: [Open access publishing](#); [Data sharing and publication](#); [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Information governance](#); [Data policy](#); [Persistent identifiers management](#); [Resource management](#); [Data sharing and publication](#); [Data governance](#); [Information security](#).

CSCCE: [Advocacy](#); [Consultation and listening](#); [Content creation and curation](#); [Content planning](#); [Landscape analysis](#); [Proposal development](#); [Technical support](#); [Financial management](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Record-keeping](#); [Teaching and training](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Evaluation and assessment](#); [Media relations](#); [Collaboration](#); [Meeting facilitation](#); [Engagement](#); [Knowledge brokering](#); [Outreach](#).

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Data Stewards

V1.1 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	13/02/2023	Initial content	Angus Whyte, Nida van Leersum, Päivi Rauste, Bojana Koteska, Laurence Horton
0.2	14/03/2023	Revised draft for discussion	as above
0.3	28/03/2023	Further revision responding to comments	as above, Karsten Kryger Hansen
0.4	1/05/2023	Further revision	as above
0.5	1/05/2023	Structured to reflect dual nature of role, responding to comments from critical friends, Data Steward Networks	Nida van Leersum, Päivi Rauste, Bojana Koteska, Laurence Horton, Angus Whyte
0.6	12/5/2023	Finalisation of the MVS draft	as above
0.7	1/10/2024	Revised to add ESCO terms and respond to feedback on training pilot	Angus Whyte, Nida van Leersum, Bojana Koteska, Laurence Horton.
0.8	7/10/2024	Restructured to reduce duplication, with WP4 input	Angus Whyte, Nida van Leersum, Lorna Wildgaard
0.9	14/10/2024	Skills terms linked to sources	Angus Whyte
1.0	11/02/2025	Skills termed edited in response to feedback (NvL, LW)	Angus Whyte
1.1	30-04-2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Sowinski Claire, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) sets out to describe competencies required for Open Science practitioner roles. Data Stewards put Open Science principles into practice and are a key role for the European Open Science Cloud. The MVS includes two variations of the role, one described as 'Coordinator' and the other 'Embedded'.

These represent two ends of a spectrum, with 'Coordinator' describing a role providing support across an organisation's research domains and units, and 'Embedded' describing a role close to a research team and to its domain-specific practices. We acknowledge that these roles can overlap, influenced by the availability of resources, and by disciplinary and organisational cultures. Data Stewardship expertise is typically distributed across a team, drawing on in-house capabilities and

external services provided to the Research Performing Organisation, e.g. by Research Infrastructures, Service Providers (e.g. scholarly communications), and Competence Centres.

In general terms, Data Stewards work with stakeholders to establish, govern and maintain processes to collect research data, make it usable for research objectives, facilitate its transformation into research output, assist in quality assurance, and support informed decision-making on its openness for reuse according to ethical, legal and social expectations.

In the EOSC specifically, in their roles as practitioners and champions of Open Science, trainers, and enablers of others in their organisation, Data Stewards are likely to be both consumers and providers of EOSC services or resources.

Coordinator Data Steward	Embedded Data Steward
<p>Coordinator Data Stewards act as a ‘centralised knowledge and communication hub’ for researchers. They advise and train on policy, guidelines, data management plans, institutional infrastructure and tools to implement FAIR and CARE principles across the organisation.</p> <p>Associated function titles: Data Steward, Data Librarian, Research Data Management Specialist, Research Data Manager, Research Data Management Consultant, Reproducibility Librarian.</p>	<p>Embedded Data Stewards serve research teams, faculties, departments, sections of organisations directly involved in producing research outputs, supporting them to plan and implement FAIR and CARE principles, meeting needs of researchers as they arise, and working with others to ensure outputs are preserved and reusable in the long term.</p> <p>Associated function titles: Data Steward, Data Manager, Data Curator, Research Data Manager</p>
<p>Essential Skills for this Role</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-domain/domain-specific knowledge of Open Science practices, policies, and regulations, translating these (when necessary) to the appropriate levels of the organisation. • Service provision to support cross-domain/domain-specific Open Science practices including: use of FAIR and CARE principles, Open Access, data optimization, data preservation, archiving, and responsible re-use. • Knowledge about Research Data Management, (personal) data governance and ethics, Open Science data publication and exchange (sharing) services, information security, and risk management. • Raising awareness of the value of good data management among data creators and users, researchers, organisational colleagues, and decision-makers. • Advising and providing support on the use of infrastructure and tools at the appropriate levels of the organisation, e.g., for data storage, data versioning, and documentation, FAIR software, and databases. • Designing and delivering training to support Open Science practices, policies, and practices. • Monitoring the research and funding ecosystem, including possible conflicting 	

motivations, drivers, and incentives among different stakeholders.

- **Knowledge/awareness of programming**, FAIR code, and FAIR software, and use of standards and ontologies.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- **Communication**
- **Conflict management/mediation** (with a patient, empathic approach)
- **Critical and analytical thinking**
- **Stakeholder engagement and networking** to translate and bridge needs
- **Creativity, curiosity, and openness** (willingness to learn)
- **Team management and project management** (results-oriented planning and organising)

Background assumptions

Main activities - Coordinator role

- Contributes to Open Science policy development by engaging with (inter)national policy-making, bringing the cross-disciplinary expertise needed for local policy development, implementation, and monitoring.
- Understands research stakeholder needs and contributes to developing, implementing, and monitoring institutional RDM policy and Data Governance, along with tools and services to support these. Promotes and communicates the importance of Open Science and FAIR to all levels within the organization (e.g., policy makers, senior management, researchers, postgraduates, etc.).
- Analyses trends in data management infrastructure, tools, and methods that potentially improve the organisation's implementation of FAIR and CARE principles to enhance support for decision-making on Open Science. Advises on (meta)data standards and contextual documentation for data archiving.

Main activities - Embedded role

- Develops Data Management Plans templates tailored for research teams and supports researchers in writing a DMP according to the relevant template. Includes provision for post-project archiving and FAIR sharing (standards, metadata, licensing, repository selection).
- Supports researchers in good practice on data and/or software/code when writing applications to funders, implements this good practice as a regular aspect of doing research, and liaises with (technical) RDM experts inside and outside the institute to adopt effective solutions to challenges.
- Advises and supports researchers on data-infrastructure and tools, and adoption of innovative techniques or tools, including those provided by relevant (inter)national data-infrastructure and tools.
- Identifies gaps and takes action if needed to ensure ethical conduct and awareness of the potential impacts of data reuse, management, and sharing

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitors RDM skills of researchers and research support staff in the institute and refers researchers to RDM related facilities and services. • Develops and delivers training tailored to learners' needs, aligned with wider institutional policies and plans. • Maintains networks of RDM and research support related colleagues. 	<p>on wider society.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advises on the use of disciplinary standards and ontologies, and relevant community practices that are applied in producing FAIR research outputs. • Supports researchers on legal and regulatory compliance aligning local practices with ethical conduct through connections with the institutional privacy officers, legal advisers, and research ethics bodies. • Provides ongoing support and guidance to researchers in following best practices for data management, ensuring ethical considerations and compliance are met. • Encourages collaboration across departments and institutions to share knowledge and improve research data management practices.
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Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Digital research objects are as FAIR and open as possible and as closed as necessary.
- Opportunities are identified for creating or connecting with professional Open Science networks at institutional, cross-institutional, regional, national, or international levels.
- Relevant competence centres with a FAIR data and Open Science support role are utilised effectively according to local needs and policies.
- Open Science skills and practices are facilitated and enhanced using, where appropriate, EOSC resources and services, including any relevant Open Educational Resources.
- Research data and other digital objects are effectively managed to ensure their suitability for archiving and sharing, and advancement of research methods appropriate to the discipline(s).

Further information

Contributors: Nida van Leersum, Päivi Rauste, Bojana Koteska, Laurence Horton, Karsten Kryger Hansen, Angus Whyte

Open Science Skills Terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Negotiate compromises](#); [Think critically](#); [Think analytically](#); [Advise others](#); [Demonstrate curiosity](#); [Adapt to change](#); [Lead others](#); [Work in teams](#); [Meet commitments](#); [Organise information, objects and resources](#).

ResearchComp: Develop networks; Teach in academic or vocational contexts; Promote open innovation; Promote the transfer of knowledge; Build mentor-mentee relationships.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data policy](#); [knowledge to contextualise fair principles to domain](#); [Service level management](#); [Data curation](#); [Preservation](#); [Open access publishing](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Information security](#); [Securing sustainable funding](#); [Software preservation](#); [Metadata exposure](#).

CSCCE: [Consultation and listening](#); [Advocacy](#); [Landscape analysis](#).

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Digital Collections Curator

V1.1 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	09/04/2024	Initial content based on Data Steward MVS and curation skills workshop	Nikos Gänsdorfer, Angus Whyte, Clara Linés
0.2	20/05/2024	Comments	Angus Whyte, Clara Linés
0.3	10/06/2024	Additional references	Angus Whyte
0.4	30/07/2024	Updated list of skills	Clara Linés, Angus Whyte
0.5	1/08/2024	Edited soft skills using terms from ESCO ontology	Angus Whyte
0.6	5/08/2024	Edited to align with learning objectives	Clara Linés, Angus Whyte
0.7	27/08/2024	Minor edits	Angus Whyte
0.8	29/08/2024	Annotated with terms from ESCO etc.	Angus Whyte
0.9	1/10/ 2024	Minor changes from reflection on training pilot	Angus Whyte
1.0	19/11/2024	Restructured to conform to new template	Angus Whyte
1.1	17/06/2025	Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) offers a framework for describing and recognising activities and skills required for open science specialists. This MVS, for Digital Collections Curators working in GLAM institutions (galleries, libraries, archives, and museums), describes expertise required to enhance the value of digital collections, e.g. to the scholarly community and the public, while respecting rights and legitimate interests of all other stakeholders. This includes individuals or groups described by collections, researchers wishing to use them, as well as host institutions and other organisations involved in maintaining access (e.g. infrastructures, funders).

A Digital Collections Curator supports digitisation and works with others to ensure the long-term preservation and reusability of data derived from collections. They advise and train researchers and other GLAM staff on policy, guidelines, data management plans, institutional infrastructure, and data management tools relevant to the domains that are the focus of digital collections in their institution. They provide support in planning and implementing principles for FAIR digital objects and for decolonisation of collections, using these principles to shape data sharing practices.

Expertise in digital collections curation is usually distributed among several people, drawing on internal skills and external services provided to the GLAM institution, e.g. by a Competence Centre or other provider. The appropriate distribution of expertise depends on cost and the availability of skills to meet needs. The document includes background assumptions about contextual factors that may influence these.

Digital Collections Curators play a key role in the EOSC. As practitioners and advocates of Open Science, and as educators and enablers of others, they are likely to be both consumers and providers of services or resources.

Digital Collections Curator

A Digital Collections Curator works with stakeholders to establish and manage processes to generate and maintain digital data collections with their associated metadata. They also make collections usable for research, facilitate their quality assurance, and their transformation into research outputs. The role also supports informed decisions about the openness of collections and data derived from them, for re-use in line with ethical, legal and social expectations.

Associated function titles: Various other job titles are relevant to the role described here, e.g. Data Curator, Data Steward, or Data Manager.

Organisational context

Digital Collection Curators serve research teams and departments in institutions that are directly involved in the publication of collection objects or the production of research results, such as:

- Museums that conduct research
- Libraries and archives
- University collections
- Research infrastructures

Essential skills for this role

Each requires understanding of the context, the processes required to perform the main activities involved, and transversal competences (“soft skills”) to engage with the various stakeholders.

- **Knowledge of principles** relating to FAIR data, Open Science, and Open Collections, the policy and legal contexts to these principles, and strategies for implementing them in diverse GLAM institutions and domains. This includes understanding of training requirements to build the essential skills for Open Collections practices, policies and procedures, including knowledge/awareness of relevant software development.
- **Knowledge and understanding of practical steps to manage Collections as Data**, to apply Open Science principles to data derived from digital collections. This includes abilities to establish and maintain good data management practices relevant to open digital collections, and to ensure data quality and long-term preservation by performing data transformation and migration, establishing processes for information security, risk management, version control, and documentation of provenance and contextual metadata about digital objects. It also includes the ability to promote the value of good data management among data producers and users, researchers, support services colleagues, and relevant committees.
- **Ability to apply FAIR principles** to collections, and to other digital objects they interoperate with, including software. This includes the capability to apply standards, ontologies, infrastructure and tools for (meta)data publishing and sharing, and for managing the associated workflows. It also includes the capability to provide open access to collections.

- **Ability to establish governance processes** to handle ethical and legal/ regulatory aspects of managing digital open collections in the GLAM sector. This requires understanding of processes to handle intellectual property rights, deal with personal data, and ensure the responsible reuse of digital objects, including through the decolonisation of collections. It also requires familiarity with sustainable business modelling approaches relevant to the sector, including appropriate levels of resource pooling and service coordination.

Soft / transversal skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- **Ability to interact positively and productively with others**, e.g. when addressing audiences, moderating discussions, or collaborating in teams and networks. This includes abilities to effect agreements, reconcile, resolve problems, and provide improvement strategies with a patient, empathetic approach.
- **Exercise critical judgement**, develop own assumptions, and establish a way of working based on critical thinking.
- **Ability to develop innovative, novel solutions**, with curiosity, openness, and a willingness to learn. This includes abilities to obtain and synthesize information to identify and explore trends, opportunities, threats (also based on intuition and creativity); and to identify alternative paths to turn ideas into action, selecting the most appropriate approach.
- **Direct activities and tasks**, establish schedules and coordinate the activities of groups and individuals to complete objectives on time and within budget.

Background assumptions

Main activities of the Digital Collections Curator

- **Identify the needs of stakeholders and contributes to the development, implementation and monitoring of institutional policies** governing research data derived from collections, together with related tools and services to support them, including through contribution to (inter)national policy development.
- **Promote and communicate** the importance of Open Collections, FAIR and decolonisation principles at all levels within the museum or collection.
- **Monitor the capabilities of researchers** to reuse open collections responsibly, and analyse trends in tools and methods that could improve the implementation of FAIR and CARE principles to support responsible reuse, providing advice on the use of disciplinary standards and ontologies to produce FAIR research outputs, and relevant (meta)data standards and contextual documentation to archive data for future reuse.
- **Support researchers and other users of collections to apply best practices** in managing data and digital objects in relevant domains, including when preparing proposals to funders, and implement these best practices in collaboration with RDM experts and stakeholders to find effective solutions to challenges.
- Advise and support researchers who use GLAM collections on **adopting relevant data infrastructures, innovative techniques and tools** to support them, including those

provided by relevant (inter)national data infrastructures and tools.

- Assist researchers using GLAM collections to **comply with laws, regulations, and policies on legal and ethical behaviour**, through liaison with institutional data protection officers, legal experts, and research ethics bodies. As a result, identify gaps and take action where needed to ensure ethical behaviour and awareness of the potential impact of data reuse, management and sharing on society.
- **Maintain networks** of colleagues involved in research data management and research support in the GLAM sector, including by co-developing and delivering training tailored to the needs of collection users and stakeholders, and by collaborating to deliver overall institutional policies and plans.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Digital collection objects are as FAIR and open as possible and as closed as necessary.
- Opportunities for the creation of or connection to professional Open Collections networks at institutional, cross-institutional, regional, national or international level are identified.
- Relevant competence centres with a FAIR Data and Open Collections support function are effectively used according to local needs and strategies.
- Open Collections skills and practices are promoted and enhanced through the use of EOSC resources and services, including relevant Open Educational Resources (OER), where appropriate.
- Collection data, metadata and related digital objects are effectively managed to ensure their suitability for archiving and sharing, and the further development of research methods appropriate to the discipline(s).

Further Information

Contributors: Nikos Gänsdorfer, Angus Whyte, Clara Linés

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Operate open-source software](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Negotiate compromises](#); [Respect the diversity of cultural values and norms](#); [Think critically](#); [Think analytically](#); [Advise others](#); [Participate actively in civic life](#); [Demonstrate curiosity](#); [Approach challenges positively](#); [Adapt to change](#); [Lead others](#); [Work in](#)

[teams](#); [Meet commitments](#); [Organise information, objects and resources](#).

ResearchComp: Manage research data; Develop networks; Teach in academic or vocational contexts; Promote open innovation; Promote the transfer of knowledge; Build mentor-mentee relationships.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data policy](#); [knowledge to contextualise fair principles to domain](#); [Service level management](#); [Data curation](#); [Preservation](#); [Open access publishing](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Information security](#); [Securing sustainable funding](#); [Software preservation](#); [Metadata exposure](#).

CSCCE: [Consultation and listening](#); [Advocacy](#); [Landscape analysis](#).

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Ethics advisor

V0.4 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1		Initial content	Luca Schirru, Valentina Colcelli, Sabrina Brizioli, Sara Casati
0.2		Draft for discussion	Above + Thomas Margoni, Angus Whyte, Laurence Horton, Dominique Green, Karolina Dostatnia, Emma Lazzeri
0.3	24/10/2024	Restructured to revised template, with ESCO terms	Bojana Koteska
0.4	17/06/2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Ethics Advisors focuses on the critical competencies required by professionals responsible for upholding ethical standards within Open Science. Ethics Advisors play a vital role in ensuring that research practices align with ethical principles while promoting openness, transparency, and adherence to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). These professionals are often tasked with balancing ethical considerations with the objectives of Open Science, including data sharing, collaboration, and accessibility, while mitigating risks related to societal, legal, and moral responsibilities.

The term "Ethics Advisor" includes professionals such as Data Ethicists, Ethics Officers, and members of Ethics Committees. These roles may vary across research institutions and projects, but all share the responsibility of ensuring that ethical guidelines are met. Ethics Advisors provide guidance on a range of issues, including research involving AI systems, dual-use technologies, animal experimentation, and broader societal impacts. They help anticipate and address potential ethical dilemmas, ensuring that research activities respect fundamental values such as accountability, transparency, inclusivity, and respect for diversity.

A key responsibility of Ethics Advisors is promoting ethical decision-making in research, while fostering a culture of openness. This includes navigating the ethical challenges posed by data protection, privacy, and the responsible use of research data. Ethics Advisors work closely with researchers, Legal Experts, and Data Protection Officers (DPOs) to create environments where ethical principles and legal compliance coexist. They provide critical input on ethical reviews, draft policies, and offer advice on complex issues such as dual-use technologies and the societal implications of scientific advancements.

In their work, Ethics Advisors promote Openness, FAIRness, and the ethical principles of responsibility/accountability, transparency, pluralism, and respect/inclusion in the realization of

Open Science within the context of research projects and organizations. Their mission is to promote accountability, transparency, and inclusivity in research, while also safeguarding against ethical risks.

Ethics advisor

Ethics Advisors play a critical role in ensuring that research practices, particularly in the context of Open Science, align with ethical standards and principles. Their primary responsibility is to promote ethical decision-making and compliance with ethical guidelines while addressing issues such as privacy, data protection, and societal impacts. Ethics Advisors navigate ethical complexities, particularly in areas involving sensitive data, AI systems, and dual-use technologies, while fostering openness and accountability. Their expertise is essential in balancing the ethical obligations required to safeguard research participants and broader societal interests, while also promoting openness and compliance with the FAIR principles.

Associated function titles: Ethics Officer, Data Protection Officer, Data Ethicist, Ethics Expert, Members of Ethics Committees.

Essential Skills for this Role

- Good understanding of OS and its practices.
- Ability to establish the appropriate strategy, frameworks and course of actions to foster and enhance OS.
- Expert knowledge of the FAIR principles and how to apply them (e.g. publishing research data in a way that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).
- Ability to identify ethical issues, raise awareness and apply the necessary measures to address the existing and applicable ethical principles (eg transparency and accountability), frameworks (e.g. RRI Framework) and codes of conduct, including but not limited to the ones concerning research (e.g. European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity -- ALLEA and the OECD's Best Practices for Ensuring Scientific Integrity and Preventing Misconduct).
- Ability to identify and address ethical issues related to personal data governance during all the data lifecycle, including but not limited to the management of personal data (e.g. collecting, storing and sharing), development and management of related policies, and knowledge of the applicable regulations on privacy and personal data protection that may concern to ethical aspects.
- Ability to raise awareness and provide instructions on (research) data ethics, and whenever needed, on specific scenarios and fields of research (e.g. in case of using data-driven technologies, this may include an expert knowledge on the rules provided in the Artificial Intelligence Act and related regulations and knowledge of best practices related to avoiding bias in data processing).
- Ability to establish connections and ease communication between different players (e.g. researchers) and bodies (e.g. legal department and the research ethics committees) when addressing ethical issues.
- Knowledge of the necessary resources to raise awareness and advise on the ethical use and management of intellectual property rights and non-personal data
-

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Leadership
- Effective communication
- Stakeholder engagement and networking
- Management skills
- Critical and Analytical thinking
- Collaboration
- Sharing knowledge and processes

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Map and identify ethical concerns inside the organization/ research project.
- Advise the organization on the compatibility of local practices with ethical principles and the existing frameworks and codes of conduct (eg FAIR, CARE principles, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, RRI framework).
- Advocate for pluralism and inclusion in Open Science.
- Set up policies, guidelines and other instruments necessary to the realization of the ethical principles concerning OS.
- Interact with stakeholders in order to ensure that research is being conducted in a responsible and transparent manner, and that consider all stakeholders rights and interests.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Raised awareness of the ethical principles in open research through the interaction with stakeholders, and advocacy activities.
- Main ethical issues are addressed in the practice of Open Science in the relevant context e.g. the organization or research project.

Further information

Contributors: Luca Schirru, Valentina Colcelli, Sabrina Brizioli, Sara Casati, Thomas Margoni, Angus Whyte, Laurence Horton, Dominique Green, Karolina Dostatnia, Emma Lazzeri, Bojana Koteska

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Perform project management](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Solve problems](#); [Identify problems](#); [Show initiative](#); [Respect confidentiality obligations](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Address an audience](#); [Advise others](#); [Motivate others](#); [Assume responsibility](#); [Plan](#); [Time management](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Negotiate compromises](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Think creatively](#); [Manage time](#); [Think critically](#); [Think analytically](#).

ResearchComp: Strategic thinking; Systemic thinking; Interact professionally.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data policy](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Research governance](#); [Data-driven decision management](#); [Information security](#); [Resource management](#).

CSCCE: [Strategy development](#); [Media relations](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Consultation and listening](#); [Meeting facilitation](#); [Engagement](#); [Record-keeping](#); [Advocacy](#); [Collaboration](#); [Knowledge brokering](#).

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Knowledge Broker

V0.3 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	June 2023	Final draft for D2.1	Emma Lazzeri, Sara di Giorgio, Dominique Green, Claire Sowinski, Gabriela Torres Ramos, Betty Evangelinou, Bojana Koteska
0.2	October 2024	Restructured to add ESCO terms and highlight essential skills	Bojana Koteska
0.3	June 2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

Knowledge brokers serve as vital intermediaries in the transfer of knowledge between experts and stakeholders. They are responsible for facilitating the dissemination of scientific information, ensuring that research findings are accessible and actionable for various audiences. Knowledge brokers promote transparency and collaboration, particularly in the context of Open Science, by bridging the gap between research and practice, enabling informed decision-making. They strive to provide unbiased and reliable information, fostering trust among stakeholders while adhering to ethical standards in knowledge sharing.

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) recognises the competencies essential for individuals or teams acting as intermediaries in the knowledge transfer process. The term “knowledge broker” refers to individuals or teams who, in a variety of contexts, facilitate the transfer of knowledge from experts to a wider audience. This practice encompasses diverse use cases with the common objective of disseminating scientific information and facilitating its use in society. Typical scenarios include appointed individual experts or expert groups informing public authorities or agencies about scientific findings, as well as aggregating research data to provide an overview of specific phenomena or fields. Such efforts support evidence-based decision-making and provide trustworthy and understandable information to laypeople.

Knowledge brokers typically use their expertise to connect stakeholders with the information and resources they need to make informed decisions. They fill the gaps between science and various stakeholders, including policymakers, practitioners, and the public. Sometimes, groups, such as committees or learned societies, undertake this role.

A notable subtype within this field is the “honest broker.” An honest broker serves as an impartial mediator, facilitating communication and decision-making among individuals or groups with differing interests or values. They maintain neutrality and bias-free positions, providing all parties with accurate information to help negotiate and find common ground. This role is especially critical in situations requiring fair and transparent processes, such as conflict resolution or public policy development.

Knowledge brokers operate within various organizational contexts, including ministries, governmental organizations, research-performing organizations, national agencies, national funding organizations, communication/media agencies, and committees or learned societies.

In relation to Open Science, the knowledge broker plays a crucial role in bridging the gap between research and practice by connecting researchers with stakeholders who can benefit from their work. They help create a more open, transparent, and collaborative research environment, leading to more effective and impactful research outcomes. This may involve collaborating closely with researchers to translate findings into actionable recommendations or providing policymakers with access to the latest accessible scientific evidence to inform decision-making. Additionally, knowledge brokers may promote Open Science practices within their organizations or communities, advocating for open access publishing, developing data-sharing policies, and supporting dissemination of research findings to a wider audience.

Knowledge broker

Associated function titles: Knowledge Broker, Honest Broker, Research Liaison, Information Specialist, Policy Advisor, Evidence Synthesis Expert, Science Communicator, Stakeholder Engagement Coordinator.

Essential Skills for this Role

- Familiarity with policy making practices and procedures.
- Understanding of open, ethical and responsible research principles.
- Managing considerable amount of information related to OS practices.
- Searching, retrieving, appraising and synthesizing evidence.
- Developing and maintaining network of researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders to help the promotion and implementation of OS practices and support for co-creation activities.
- Providing training and education to researchers, policymakers, and public citizens about OS practices.
- Evaluating research findings and identifying potential conflicts of interest.
- Tailoring resources to local needs and assessing the implementation context.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Communication
- Collaboration
- Leadership
- Self-confidence
- Citizens and stakeholders engagement

- Influencing
- Negotiation and diplomacy
- Problem-solving
- Innovative thinking
- Analytical and research skills
- Adaptability to changes
- Stakeholder management and influencing
- Facilitation

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Bridging the interface between science and policy by ensuring mutual understanding among these parties.
- Aligning the needs of the policy community with the evidence synthesis provided.
- Ensuring that the policy community have a good understanding of the implications of the evidence proffered.
- Ensuring the quality and transparency of evidence synthesis.
- Ensuring the evidence synthesis has appropriate expert inputs.
- Identifying options and providing advice from a scientific viewpoint.
- Identifying constraints, uncertainties and caveats.
- Contextualising the FAIR and OS principles to specific domains.
- Identifying strengths and weaknesses in how OS is applied.
- Identifying needs for change in OS policy or practice in relevant research domains.
- Ensuring all actors are engaged in co-creation actions.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Information needs of referenced stakeholders/interlocutors are identified and addressed, by bridging specialised scientific data and information and facilitating the stakeholders' understanding and correct interpretation of this information.
- Concrete policy options are drafted through analysis and evaluation that is based as much as possible on co-creation, continuous knowledge exchange and capacity building.
- Knowledge producers and users are facilitated in an objective and transparent manner, by translating science into accessible and policy-usable knowledge.
- Open Science and FAIR principles are applied in the knowledge production chain to enhance the uptake into public policy of scientifically developed knowledge.

- Policymakers are helped to identify options, and understand the likely impact of choices, by providing advice from a scientific viewpoint.
- Researchers are helped to understand the potential impact on policy makers of their outcomes.
- Through advocacy, FAIR and Open Science principles become related to the organisation's local policies and processes including its research practices and goals.

Further information

Contributors: Emma Lazzeri, Sara di Giorgio, Dominique Green, Claire Sowinski, Gabriela Torres Ramos, Betty Evangelinou, Bojana Koteska

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Synthesise information](#); [Develop professional network with researchers and scientists](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Promote the participation of citizens in scientific and research activities](#); [Mentor individuals](#); [Teach in academic or vocational contexts](#); [Evaluate research activities](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Organise information, objects and resources](#); [Demonstrate curiosity](#); [Conduct web searches](#); [Critically evaluate information and its sources](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Make decisions](#); [Motivate others](#); [Show confidence](#); [Plan](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Show empathy](#); [Negotiate compromises](#); [Promote ideas, products, services](#); [Respect the diversity of cultural values and norms](#); [Manage time](#).

ResearchComp: Promote citizen science; Mobilise resources.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data policy](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Information security](#); [Open access publishing](#); [Open peer review](#); [Open innovation](#); [Research integrity, attribution, impact awareness](#); [Research governance](#); [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Training in open and fair methods](#).

CSCCE: [Consultation and listening](#); [Data analysis](#); [Landscape analysis](#); [Advocacy](#); [Collaboration](#); [Knowledge brokering](#); [Engagement](#); [Moderation, mediation and intervention](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Evaluation and assessment](#); [Cultural competence](#); [Meeting facilitation](#); [Record-keeping](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Social media](#); [Content planning](#).

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<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-018-0143-3>

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Legal expert

V0.4 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1		Initial content	Luca Schirru, Valentina Colcelli, Sabrina Brizioli, Sara Casati
0.2		Draft for discussion	Above + Thomas Margoni, Angus Whyte, Laurence Horton, Dominique Green, Karolina Dostatnia, Emma Lazzeri
0.3			
0.4	17/06/2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for legal experts provides a structured understanding of the critical competencies required by professionals responsible for ensuring legal compliance within Open Science. These individuals play a key role in managing the complex legal landscapes surrounding both personal and non-personal data, safeguarding the rights of third parties while promoting openness and adherence to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Legal experts must navigate the tension between the existing property-based legal framework and the openness essential to achieving Open Science objectives, particularly in areas such as Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and data protection.

The term "Legal Expert" encompasses a variety of professionals, including Legal Consultants, Lawyers, Regulatory Affairs Managers, Data Protection Officers (DPOs), and Technology Transfer/IP Lawyers. Each role has varying degrees of legal authority, with some professionals, such as Regulatory Affairs Managers, not always licensed to provide legal advice yet having significant expertise in legal matters. A key aspect of this role is ensuring compliance with regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), while also facilitating open access to research materials, data reuse, and collaboration. Legal experts also assist in aligning organizations with legal standards, mitigating risks related to privacy, intellectual property, and contractual obligations.

An important responsibility of legal experts is bridging the gap between the goals of Open Science and regulatory requirements. They work closely with researchers and institutions to ensure that the use of protected materials and sensitive data complies with existing laws, while promoting openness and facilitating the lawful sharing and reuse of scientific information. Their work often includes drafting agreements, managing licensing, ensuring the preservation of protected materials, and advising on data-sharing practices.

The mission of a legal expert in Open Science is to promote openness and FAIRness in a legal system predominantly centred on exclusive property rights, while simultaneously mitigating legal risks

through a proactive approach to compliance with personal and non-personal data regulations. In doing so, they contribute significantly to building a transparent and accessible research environment, which is critical for the advancement of Open Science.

Legal expert

Legal experts play a critical role in ensuring that research practices, particularly in the context of Open Science, comply with complex legal frameworks. Their primary responsibility is to safeguard the rights of third parties by ensuring adherence to national, regional, and international regulations governing both personal and non-personal data. Legal experts manage the tension between traditional intellectual property laws, which are often based on exclusive ownership, and the openness required to advance Open Science goals. Their expertise is essential in mitigating legal risks, ensuring data protection, and promoting openness and compliance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

Associated function titles: Legal Consultant, Lawyer, Regulatory Affairs Manager, Technology Transfer/IP Lawyer, Data Protection Officer, Legal Advisor.

Essential Skills for this Role

- Good understanding of OS and its practices.
- Ability to establish the appropriate strategy, frameworks and course of actions to foster and enhance OS.
- Expert knowledge of the FAIR principles and how to apply them, especially the one concerning (re)usability e.g. copyright licensing rules and existing frameworks like the Creative Commons licenses.
- Ability to identify ethical issues and apply the necessary measures to address the existing and applicable ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct, including but not limited to the ones concerning research, e.g. the RRI Framework and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA).
- Ability to address legal issues related to personal data governance, including but not limited to the management of personal data; development and management of policies on privacy and data protection, e.g. consent forms, data policies, etc; and expert knowledge on the application of regulations concerning privacy and personal data protection.
- Ability to develop, negotiate and assess data use agreements, based on expert knowledge of the regulations that commonly govern these documents.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Problem-solving
- Effective communication
- Critical and Analytical thinking
- Collaboration
- Translating needs/bridging function

- Research skills
- Flexibility and adaptability
- Proactiveness and responsiveness

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Promotes and supports Open Access and other Open Science related legal and ethical principles.
- Monitors the regulatory landscape and national policies concerning OS e.g. GDPR, ODD, DGA, Data Act proposal, IPR-related directives and regulations.
- Assesses and addresses legal risks concerning Intellectual Property Rights, e.g., Personal and Non-Personal Data Protection and Governance, Licensing and Information Security.
- Promotes Open Science by employing available instruments e.g. licensing frameworks, rights retention strategies; and normative tools e.g. copyright exceptions and limitations.
- Develops policies, contracts and other instruments needed to put into action the legal rules and ethical principles concerning OS.
- Advises the organisation about the compatibility of local practices with current legal frameworks.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- The organisation is able to adopt existing licensing frameworks e.g. Creative Commons, and enjoys the free uses allowed under the existing legal framework e.g. copyright limitations and exceptions.
- The organisation is equipped with policies, contracts and other instruments needed to apply the legal rules and ethical principles concerning Open Science.

Further information

Contributors: Luca Schirru, Valentina Colcelli, Sabrina Brizioli, Sara Casati, Thomas Margoni, Angus Whyte, Laurence Horton, Dominique Green, Karolina Dostatnia, Emma Lazzeri

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Manage Intellectual Property Rights](#); [Apply Research Ethics and Scientific Integrity Principles in Research Activities](#); [Manage Open Publications](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Solve Problems](#); [Identify Problems](#); [Show Initiative](#); [Comply with Regulations](#); [Negotiate Compromises](#); [Resolve Conflicts](#); [Organise Information, Objects and Resources](#); [Moderate a Discussion](#); [Think Critically](#); [Think Analytically](#); [Build](#)

[Networks](#); [Demonstrate Intercultural Competence](#); [Demonstrate Trustworthiness](#); [Think Quickly](#); [Demonstrate Willingness to Learn](#); [Attend to Detail](#); [Demonstrate Curiosity](#).

ResearchComp: Strategic thinking; Systemic thinking; Analytical thinking; Cope with pressure; Plan self-organisation.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Knowledge to contextualise FAIR principles to domain](#); [Information security](#); [Data policy](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Data driven decision management](#); [Research integrity, attribution, impact awareness](#); [Research governance](#); [Change management](#).

CSCCE: [Strategy development](#); [Content planning](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Consultation and listening](#); [Collaboration](#).

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Whyte, A. & Ashley, K. (2017). *Deliverable D7.1: Skills landscape analysis and competence model*. EOSCPilot. Annex A. *Indicative Scope of data stewardship competences and their mapping to other frameworks*. pp. 60-63 (mentioning other sources, like the EDISON Data Science Competence Framework, RDA Interest Group Educ. & Training in Data Handling (Wiki), and Purdue University/SAPP Nelson – Data Information Literacy, which also contributed to these skills).

Whyte, A., Vries, J., Thorat, R., Kuehn, E., Sipos, G., Cavalli, V., Kalaitzi, V., Ashley, K. (2018). *Deliverable D7.3: Skills and Capability Framework*. EOSCPilot. Open Science stewardship competences and capabilities table. p.39-40.

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Policy maker – Evidence-based policy

V0.7 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	09/12/2022	Initial content	Arnaud Gingold, Karla Avanço, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski,
0.2	15/12/2022	Draft for discussion	Arnaud Gingold, Karla Avanço, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte, Dominique Green
0.3	17/01/2023	Revised to split evidence-based policy maker from OS policy maker, following discussion in WP2, WP3. Removed division of soft skills vs technical competences	Katerina Kyprianou, Ognjen Prnjat, Joy Davidson, Luca Schirru, Emma Lazzeri, Angus Whyte, Dominique Green
0.4	6/02/2023	“type 1’ and ‘type 2’ reordered to match survey questionnaire	Angus Whyte
0.5	21/10/2024	Moved essential skills to top, added ESCO terms	Bojana Koteska
0.6	27/11/2024	Soft skills edited, minor edits for length	Angus Whyte
0.7	17/06/2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) sets out to describe a shared framework for recognizing the competencies required for policymakers in advancing Open Science. Policymakers play a key role in creating the strategic conditions that promote Open Science practices and ensure their integration into national and international research frameworks. They work with stakeholders to establish, implement, and govern policies that support the adoption of Open Science, providing the necessary frameworks, resources, and partnerships that enable the transparent, collaborative, and accessible use of research data.

In the Open Science ecosystem, policymakers serve as both advocates and enablers of Open Science, ensuring that the principles of transparency, accessibility, and collaboration are embedded within research practices and governance structures. Their role is crucial in fostering the use of Open Science in evidence-based decision-making, aligning policy goals with scientific research outcomes.

The MVS for policymakers recognises two complementary but distinct roles. The first focuses on developing policies that support Open Science, described as ‘Research Policy/Decision Maker Facilitating Open Science’. The second is focused on using credible research data to inform specific policy decisions and is described as ‘Evidence-informed Policy and Decision Maker.’

Policy maker – Evidence-based policy

Evidence-informed Policy and Decision Makers gather, assess, and synthesize credible research data to design policies addressing specific societal or scientific issues. They ensure that policy decisions are data-driven and aligned with the principles of Open Science, considering the relevance and quality of evidence to inform their decisions.

Associated function titles: Policy Designer, Open Science Data Analyst, Policy Advisor.

Essential skills and competences

- Basic understanding of OS/ FAIR principles.
- Knowledge of OS services, resources and research practices that produce evidence relevant to the decision-making context.
- Expertise in applying evidence from OS to the decision-making context, considering the opportunities, limitations, and constraints.
- Knowledge management: synthesising outputs of research and consultation, identifying their relevance to specific issues and stakeholders.
- Basic knowledge of research integrity principles, frameworks and ethical codes.
- Knowledge of the responsible use of data-driven technologies.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Negotiating with stakeholders to articulate rights and responsibilities for policy implementation.
- Advocating policy measures by addressing the audiences needed to mobilise key enablers and other human resources.
- Mobilising and managing financial and material resources, demonstrating trustworthiness.
- Complying with regulations and respecting confidentiality obligations.
- Using initiative to formulate policy implementation strategies.
- Applying systemic thinking to critically evaluate evidence and its sources.

Background assumptions

Main activities – Decision-maker role

- Identifies available OS outcomes relevant to an issue that requires a policy.
- Collaborates with expert communities for elicitation, review and evaluation of data and design of a policy.
- Deploys appropriate policy outcome monitoring and evaluation designs based on OS evidence.

- Ensures inclusiveness in evidence's production and evaluation.
- Promotes and supports OS as a source of evidence.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Thorough research is carried out of available open data to identify information that is timely, relevant and credible.
- Citizens and researchers are consulted appropriately considering the specificity of their activity (scientist vs. politician) and role (honest broker vs. issue advocate).
- Gathered information is synthesised to enable design of a policy relevant to the specific issue.

Further information

Contributors: Arnaud Gingold, Karla Avanço, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte, Dominique Green, Katerina Kyprianou, Ognjen Prnjat, Joy Davidson, Luca Schirru, Emma Lazzeri, Bojana Koteska, Angus Whyte.

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Synthesise information](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Exercise rights and responsibilities](#); [Manage time](#); [Plan](#); [Think critically](#); [Critically evaluate information and its sources](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Respect confidentiality obligations](#)

ResearchComp: Mobilise resources.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Knowledge to contextualise FAIR principles to domain](#); [Resource management](#); [Data policy](#); [Data governance](#); [Privacy governance](#); [Data driven decision management](#).

CSCCE: [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Evaluation and assessment](#); [Landscape analysis](#).

Reference sources

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Engelhardt, C., Barthauer, R., Biernacka, K., Coffey, A., Cornet, R., Danciu, A., Demchenko, Y. et al. (2022), *How to Be FAIR with Your Data*. <https://www.univerlag.uni-goettingen.de/handle/3/isbn-978-3-86395-539-7>.

European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation and EOSC Executive

Board (2021), *Digital Skills for FAIR and Open Science: Report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group*. LU: Publications Office.

<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>.

EOSC Glossary Interest Group (2020). *EOSC Glossary*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4472643>.

Topp, L., Mair, D., Smillie, L., & Cairney, P. (2018). *Knowledge Management for Policy Impact: The Case of the European Commission's Joint Research Centre*. *Palgrave Communications* 4 (1): 1-10.

<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-018-0143-3>.

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Policy maker - Research Policy

V0.7 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	09/12/2022	Initial content	Arnaud Gingold, Karla Avanço, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski,
0.2	15/12/2022	Draft for discussion	Arnaud Gingold, Karla Avanço, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte, Dominique Green
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In the Open Science ecosystem, policymakers serve as both advocates and enablers of Open Science, ensuring that the principles of transparency, accessibility, and collaboration are embedded within research practices and governance structures. Their role is crucial in fostering the use of Open Science in evidence-based decision-making, aligning policy goals with scientific research outcomes.

The MVS for policymakers recognises two complementary but distinct roles. The first focuses on developing policies that support Open Science, described as ‘Research Policy/Decision Maker

Facilitating Open Science'. The second is focused on using credible research data to inform specific policy decisions and is described as 'Evidence-informed Policy and Decision Maker.'

Policy maker for research

Research Policy/Decision Makers act as facilitators for the development and promotion of Open Science policies. They create frameworks and provide the necessary support to promote the adoption of OS practices at national and international levels. This includes mobilizing resources, building partnerships, and ensuring policies align with OS principles like FAIR.

Associated function titles: Research Policy Maker, Science Policy Facilitator, Strategic Policy Advisor.

Essential skills and competences

- In-depth understanding of science practice, OS and FAIR principles and practices.
- Expertise in establishing appropriate strategies, frameworks and courses of action to foster and enhance OS.
- Ability to relate OS practices to the interests of Research Performing Organisations, Funders, and other stakeholders.
- Ability to assess the financial sustainability of policy outcomes.
- Knowledge about Intellectual property rights and non-personal data management.
- Knowledge of Ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct applicable to research.
- Knowledge of legal issues related to data governance including data use agreements and personal data regulations.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Negotiating with stakeholders to articulate rights and responsibilities for policy implementation.
- Advocating policy measures by addressing the audiences needed to mobilise key enablers and other human resources.
- Mobilising and managing financial and material resources, demonstrating trustworthiness.
- Complying with regulations and respecting confidentiality obligations.
- Using initiative to formulate policy implementation strategies.
- Applying systemic thinking to critically evaluate evidence and its sources.

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Promotes and supports OS.
- Engages all the appropriate target audiences & key stakeholders.

- Identifies actions to advance policies on FAIR and OS at the relevant level (e.g. national, thematic).
- Understands the importance of addressing gaps in provision of digital skills for FAIR and OS.
- Promotes digital skills for data intensive science transferable across different sectors.
- Sets up policies or a strategic framework which serve to promote a preferred course of action and could include financial support research.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Frameworks and incentives are established to enhance the implementation of Open Science, with the financial commitment to ensure its continuous support.
- Appropriate partnerships with key stakeholders are established.
- A team of Open Science experts is built up to inform policy implementation

Further information

Contributors: Arnaud Gingold, Karla Avanço, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte, Dominique Green, Katerina Kyprianou, Ognjen Prnjat, Joy Davidson, Luca Schirru, Emma Lazzeri, Bojana Koteska, Angus Whyte

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ESCO Research Skills: [Perform project management](#); [Show entrepreneurial spirit](#); [Promote the participation of citizens in scientific and research activities](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Solve problems](#); [Identify problems](#); [Show initiative](#); [Plan](#); [Manage financial and material resources](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Respect confidentiality obligations](#); [Exercise rights and responsibilities](#)

ResearchComp: Strategic thinking; Systemic thinking; Mobilise resources; Promote citizen science.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Knowledge to contextualise FAIR principles to domain](#); [Resource management](#); [Information security](#); [Data policy](#); [Data governance](#); [Privacy governance](#).

CSCCE: [Strategy development](#); [Content planning](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Engagement](#); [Advocacy](#); [Financial management](#).

Reference sources

OECD (2020), *Building Digital Workforce Capacity and Skills for Data-Intensive Science*. OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers 90. <https://doi.org/10.1787/e08aa3bb-en>.

Engelhardt, C., Barthauer, R., Biernacka, K., Coffey, A., Cornet, R., Danciu, A., Demchenko, Y. et al. (2022), *How to Be FAIR with Your Data*. <https://www.univerlag.uni-goettingen.de/handle/3/isbn-978-3-86395-539-7>.

European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation and EOSC Executive Board (2021), *Digital Skills for FAIR and Open Science: Report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group*. LU: Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>.

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Researcher - Early Career

V0.6 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1		Initial content	Dominique Green, Saba Sharma, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia
0.2		Draft for discussion	As above
0.3		Draft for internal review	As above + Luca Schirru
0.4	8/10/2024	Added ESCO terms and updated the MVS layout	Dominique Green
0.5	16/02/2025	Response to comments by Eva Mendez	Angus Whyte
0.6	17/06/2025	Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

Early career researchers for the purposes of this Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) include PhD students, postdoctoral researchers, and other researchers within 5 to 8 years of completion of their doctorate degree. The MVS addresses the competencies and skills needed by researchers in the early stages of their research career as is related to Open OS.

A key principle of Open Science (OS) is that research is conducted openly and transparently leading to better science. Subsequently, researchers at every career stage have a key role in the promotion of Open Science and its practice. Researchers have a key role in the promotion of Open Science (OS) and its practice. Not only do early career researchers contribute to the wider uptake of skills, building their own individual skills and organizational capacities, openness is at the core of the researchers role. They are an integral part of all production and dissemination of knowledge.

OS can be facilitated via data sharing, exploring and reusing data and, data publication, and making codes available, promoting open research through peer review, and reproducible research. By adopting OS approaches, researchers work to ensure that the benefits which openness brings, such as the accessibility, reproducibility and transparency of research, are available to students, colleagues, and to society as a whole.

Early Career Researcher

Associated function titles:

- Occupations at levels R1 and R2 in the [European Framework for Research Careers](#), e.g. PhD students, Post-doctoral researchers
- Other researchers (working outside of academia and research councils)

Essential Skills for this Role

- Good understanding of OS and its practices, in a discipline-specific context, particularly knowledgeable of policies, opportunities and practices of OS (e.g., open access, data storage and archival).
- Sound knowledge of the data life cycle and adequate capacity to implement FAIR principles using discipline-specific resources.
- Ability to assess FAIRness of existing data, and to capture, process, analyse, and preserve data according to OS principles.
- Experience in using tools for conducting research, managing and sharing research output.
- Commitment to undertaking training on digital-oriented research practices.
- Research management skills: Ability to design an open research strategy, implement an open research vision, and coordinate research activities that embed open science principles.
- Entrepreneurial skills: Ability to identify and apply for OS funding opportunities; ability to acquire funding that furthers open science goals, writing grants and funding applications.
- Good understanding of legal aspects of research relevant to their field of expertise, and of relevant Open Science practices. These include, but not limited to: Intellectual Property Rights e.g. copyright, patents, and trade secrets; and other Non-Personal Data e.g. use of IoT data and research data; Personal Data Protection and Governance e.g. processing Personal Data under the current legal framework, and following existing policies on Data Protection, Privacy, (Open) Licensing rules and frameworks.
- Good understanding of ethical principles e.g. transparency, diversity, and accountability; and of best practices e.g. avoiding bias in data processing when using data-driven technologies applicable to their field of expertise. These include the general ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct applicable to research e.g., the RRI Framework; the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.
- Ability to balance personal and non-personal data protection requirements with Open Science/FAIR principles.

Soft/ transversal skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Cooperation and collaboration
- Ethical orientation to open science principles and their broader social goals
- Adaptable: ability to build openness into the research process, staying up to date with research processes, software, data management systems, etc.
- Time management: incorporate Open Science/FAIR practices in a timely way during the research cycle
- Communication and interpersonal skills: engage with a variety of stakeholders
- Project management
- Presentation skills

- Critical thinking

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Promotes and supports Open Science (OS), e.g. by joining and supporting its initiatives.
- Produces research data for management, analysis, use, reuse, and dissemination.
- Collaborates with informal and formal research groups, including training students and other early career researchers on OS.
- Interacts with the general public to enhance the impact of science and research.
- Communicates research for scholarly and societal impact.
- Publishes research openly, providing metadata, data, code publicly available.

Open Science activities are apparent in all aspects of the early career researchers work flow. In conducting research, the early career researcher participates in additional activities essential to Open Science, including the following:

- Open access publishing, which can be applied to peer-reviewed journal articles, theses, book chapters, monographs, and conference papers.
- Opens data, which involves making all data that are necessary to reproduce reported results publicly accessible and digitally shareable.
- Opens materials, which includes having all components of the research methodology.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- By adopting the Open Science (OS) approach in their work, the early career researcher ensures that their research is carried out with a high degree of transparency, collegiality, and research integrity.
- By adopting OS approaches and practices, research input and outputs are shared.
- FAIR principles and methods are adopted and practiced.
- Scientific information is used more efficiently.
- The dissemination of knowledge is improved.
- Reproducibility of scientific findings is improved.

Further information

Contributors: Dominique Green, Saba Sharma, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia, Luca Schirru, Angus Whyte, Eva Méndez

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. Terms are selected to add further information and to aid discovery of this MVS (an extended list is added at the foot of this document). Sources: European Skills, Competences and

Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Manage open publications](#); [Operate open source software](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Manage research data](#); [Draft scientific or academic papers and technical documentation](#); [Perform scientific research](#); [Apply for research funding](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Perform project management](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Think critically](#); [Demonstrate willingness to learn](#); [Manage financial and material resources](#); [Show entrepreneurial spirit](#); [Comply with regulation](#); [Respect confidentiality obligations](#); [Build networks](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Work in teams](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Show determination](#); [Adapt to change](#); [Accept criticism and guidance](#); [Demonstrate curiosity](#); [Think innovately](#); [Keep an open mind](#); [Manage time](#); [Address an audience](#); [Plan](#); [Lead others](#); [Meet commitments](#); [Organise information, objects and resources](#); [Build team spirit](#); [Show initiative](#)

ResearchComp: [Disciplinary expertise](#); [Analytical thinking](#); [Manage personal professional development](#); [Strategic thinking](#); [Systemic thinking](#); [Write research documents](#); [Develop networks](#); [Interact professionally](#); [Communicate to the broad public](#); [Disseminate results to the research community](#).

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data policy](#); [Data costs management](#); [data sharing and publication](#); [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Domain knowledge to contextualise data handling](#); [Research integrity process design](#); [Data processing](#); [Data curation](#); [Data costs management](#); [crediting research contributors](#); [data processing](#); [open peer review](#); [persistent identifiers management](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Research governance](#).

CSCCE: [Strategy development](#); [Content planning](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Engagement](#); [Project/programme design](#); [Collaboration](#); [Consultation and listening](#); [Speaking and presenting](#).

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(editor), Stoy, L. (editor), Publications Office, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>.

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Researcher - Senior

V0.6 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1		Initial content	Saba Sharma, Dominique Green, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia
0.2		Draft for discussion	As above
0.3		Draft v3	As above + comments from Paula Martinez Lavanchy, Massimo Cocco,
0.4		Draft for internal review	As above + comments from Paula Martinez Lavanchy, Massimo Cocco, Luca Schirru
0.5	9/10/2024	Revised to add Open Science skills terms and update the MVS layout	Dominique Green
0.6	17/06/2025	Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

This Skillset profile focuses on Open Science (OS) skills and activities relevant for senior researchers. Senior researchers are typically defined as those who are established within their fields, developed a level of independence, and typically lead research projects. The profile highlights the role of Senior Researchers in setting the agenda by implementing OS policies, raising awareness, and mentoring and training Early Career Researchers in the principles of Open Science.

Senior Researchers are key actors within institutional contexts in promoting Open Science and FAIR principles among research colleagues, and in supporting them ensuring that relevant data or other research outputs are made FAIR/Open in accordance with domain standards and stakeholder expectations. They are expected to be catalysts for change in how research is conducted by centring open science practices, and show leadership through implementing Open Science policies in their own research projects and teams, as well as their role in mentoring and training students, raising awareness of open science among undergraduate and masters students, and acting as a bridge between the scientific community and technical services. To achieve this mission, Senior Researchers are expected to possess an expert-level understanding of Open Science and FAIR principles and their applications in their discipline-specific contexts, including regulatory, ethical and policy requirements. In turn, they need to be supported by research organizations in this mission, in the form of Open Science policies and relevant resources to implement them.

Senior researcher

Organisational context:

- Governmental organizations
- National agencies
- National funding organizations
- Research Performing Organizations

Essential Skills for this Role

- Realise discipline-specific applications of Open Science principles and identify practices relevant to them at every stage of the research workflow.
- Outline relevant practices of Open Science and FAIR principles and create guidelines for their research teams.
- Ability to identify and track open research funding and acquire funding that furthers Open Science goals through writing grants and funding applications.
- Mentoring and training researchers and students in Open Science practices throughout the research life-cycle and nurturing professional development of Early Career Researchers in accordance with Open Science principles.
- Ability to build professional collaboration frameworks between academia and industry or other sectors to enable Open Science, build research projects that embed open science principles throughout.
- Ability to collect, annotate and document data and software, create metadata, use relevant taxonomies, handle big data sets and use existing repositories.
- Developing expert-level awareness of legal aspects related to Intellectual Property Rights e.g. copyright, patents and trade secrets; and to other Non-Personal Data e.g. IoT data and research data, Personal Data Protection and Governance e.g. processing Personal Data under the current legal framework. Managing data use agreements and policies on Data Protection, Privacy, and (Open) Licensing rules and frameworks, as well as the use of data and information which may be considered sensitive.
- Developing expert-level awareness of ethical principles e.g., transparency, diversity and accountability; and best practices e.g., avoiding bias in data processing when using data-driven technologies applicable to their field of expertise. These include general ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct applicable to research e.g. the RRI Framework; the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.
- Applying open publication practices, such as publishing preprints, publishing in open access journals and platforms, ensuring data and code are available in open repositories to the extent possible.
- Engaging with stakeholders outside academia to maximize research impact.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Effective communication
- Ability to provide constructive feedback
- Research management and leadership
- Time and people management
- Teamwork and collaboration
- Problem-solving
- Research integrity

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Applies Open Science policies, strategies and best practices.
- Promotes and supports Open Science principles in their disciplinary fields by training other researchers in open science practices, methods and skills.
- Contributes to education and professional development of students and Early Career Researchers by developing curricula and programs in Open Science methods, including data management.
- Provides researchers in their group with appropriate knowledge and support to understand regulatory, ethical and policy requirements affecting their research.
- Designs and manages research activities.
- Builds and coordinates research teams.
- Establishes collaboration network.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

The main objective of the Senior Researcher is to conduct and oversee high quality and reproducible research, undertaken with integrity. Given their role in supervision, education, hiring, journal editing, peer review, and informing institutional policies, Senior Researchers can establish a research environment that supports and implements Open Science. Crucially, Senior Researchers have a responsibility to manage and nurture Early Career Researchers. This can be achieved via the following:

- Applies Open Science policies, strategies and best practices.
- Promotes and supports Open Science principles in their disciplinary fields by training other researchers in open science practices, methods and skills.
- Contributes to education and professional development of students and Early Career Researchers by developing curricula and programs in Open Science methods, including data management.
- Provides researchers in their group with appropriate knowledge and support to understand regulatory, ethical and policy requirements affecting their research.

- Designs and manages research activities.
- Builds and coordinates research teams.
- Establishes collaboration network.

Further information

Contributors: Saba Sharma, Dominique Green, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia, Luca Schirru, Angus Whyte

Open Science skills terms

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ESCO Research Skills: [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Manage research data](#); [Synthesise information](#); [Apply for research funding](#); [Mentor individuals](#); [Teach in academic or vocational contexts](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Manage open publications](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Promote the participation of citizens in scientific and research activities](#); [Perform project management](#); [Integrate gender dimension in research](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Report facts](#); [Manage financial and material resources](#); [Show entrepreneurial spirit](#); [Advise others](#); [Address an audience](#); [Instruct others](#); [Build networks](#); [Organise information, objects and resources](#); [Respect confidentiality obligations](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Critically evaluate information and its sources](#); [Think critically](#); [Show empathy](#); [Lead others](#); [Adapt to change](#); [Meet commitments](#); [Plan](#); [Show initiative](#); [Assume responsibility](#); [Make decisions](#); [Manage time](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Negotiate compromises](#); [Show commitment](#); [Work in teams](#); [Build team spirit](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Show determination](#); [Solve problems](#); [Think analytically](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#).

ResearchComp: Abstract thinking; Strategic thinking; Write research documents; Mobilise resources; Promote open innovation; Teach in academic or vocational contexts; Promote the transfer of knowledge; Communicate to the broad public; Increase the impact of science on policy and society; Negotiate; Promote open access publishing; Participate in publication process; Manage personal professional development; Promote citizen science; Critical thinking; Evaluate research; Plan self-organisation; Ensure wellbeing at work.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Knowledge to contextualise fair principles to domain](#); [Mentoring on open and fair methods](#); [Training in open and fair methods](#); [Crediting research contributors](#); [Data analysis](#); [Data categorisation](#); [Data curation](#); [Data destruction](#); [Data discovery](#); [Data driven decision management](#); [Data harmonization](#); [Data sharing and publication](#); [Depositing in repository](#); [Evaluating repositories for data deposit/sharing](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Data policy](#); [Open peer review](#); [Stakeholder engagement on societal impact](#); [Research management](#); [Research integrity](#).

[attribution, impact awareness](#); [Data sharing and publication](#).

CSCCE: [Strategy development](#); [Content creation and curation](#); [Content planning](#); [Record keeping](#); [Landscape analysis](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Proposal development](#); [Advancement, growth and sustainability](#); [Collaboration](#); [Data analysis](#); [Advancement, growth and sustainability](#); [Engagement](#); [Evaluation and assessment](#).

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Research Infrastructure Professional

V0.6 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	31/03/2023	Initial content	Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Päivi Rauste, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Claire Sowinski, Gabriela Torres-Ramos
0.2	27/04/2023	Review	Marialuisa Lavitrano, Enrico Guarini, Sara Casati
0.3	04/05/2023	Review additions integrated ELSI aspects integrated	Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Päivi Rauste, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Claire Sowinski, Gabriela Torres-Ramos
0.4	09/05/2023	Review by task leader	Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Angus Whyte
0.5	19/11/2024	Conversion to a new template	Elena Sokolova
0.6	17/06/2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

Research Infrastructures (RIs) support “research communities to conduct research and foster innovation” and constitute a major component in building an OS environment in so far as they aim at both “skilling researchers” and providing a wide range of “supporting staff”. RIs pool together tools, Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) and good practices to monitor and make accessible the entire research process.

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Research Infrastructure (RI) professionals therefore considers the specificities of the functions represented in such organizations with regard to Open Science (OS). The functions can be diverse and correspond to many function titles, however, as these functions are in great part defined by the organization’s role, the content, context, and prospect of the missions are common to all RI professionals. The MVS for RI professionals proposes therefore a generic description of the role, which can be applied with adjustments to various functions. More detailed descriptions of specific functions can be found in other MVS, e.g. in the MVS for data stewards operating in RIs.

The OS missions of RI professionals therefore entail: spreading a Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and OS culture; managing the RI; providing, handling and maintaining services, resources, and tools; harmonizing and improving a common EU OS space; supporting and monitoring FAIRification; providing training, sharing best practices, and building a research community.

Research Infrastructures professionals

Research Infrastructure (RI) professionals contribute to open science development by being “operators who have experience and insights into scientific or technical issues whilst also being a professional manager”. RI professionals also play a specific role in coordinating and engaging the scientific community.

Associated function titles: Infrastructure manager, Project manager, Service manager, Chief Technology Officer, Data manager, Data steward, Researcher.

Essential Skills for this Role

- Expertise and competence in Responsible Research & Innovation, OS and research governance, based on knowledge of diverse EU research policies and systems.
- Technical knowledge and skills needed for service development and provision, including data use agreements, information security and risk management.
- Staff management and project management.
- Ability to plan and implement FAIR and open science principles and reproducible research by empowering people to implement transparent, accountable and sustainable processes that meet scientific communities’ identified needs.
- Expertise in developing guidelines in multidisciplinary areas.
- Fostering a common vision among various stakeholders.
- Ability to understand ethical and legal implications of research, including:
 - Intellectual property rights and non-personal data management.
 - Knowledge of Ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct.
 - Legal issues related to personal data governance.
 - Responsible use of data-driven technologies.
- Ability to create, plan, coordinate public events and information pathways.

Soft/ transversal skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Networking in inclusive/pluralist/participatory environments.
- Community engagement expertise.
- Team building and teamwork.
- Leadership and coordination.
- Sharing knowledge and processes.
- Pedagogical skills.

- Analytical and research skills
- Flexibility and adaptability
- Proactiveness and responsiveness

Background assumptions

Main activities

Service

- Provide knowledge-related facilities and resources such as collections, archives or scientific data infrastructures; computing systems, communication networks, and any other infrastructure.
- Provide technological alignment, standards implementation.
- Provide guidance about FAIR principles and FAIR implementation.
- Ensure technical policy consistency throughout projects and activities of the RI.

Support

- Coordinate and engage the research community's relevant stakeholders with a special attention to young generation.
- Set up and offer foundational and specialized digital skills training for scientific community, data professionals, ELSI experts, Data Protection Officers.
- Facilitate in-person and online training and development of communities of practice.
- Support the application of RRI principles through the anticipation of impact and the consideration of inclusiveness and transparency dimensions of research.
- Instruct researchers on open licensing and open software according to the legislation on the reuse of public funded research data.

Coordination

- Foster new partnerships and innovative services through internal and external collaboration.
- Share knowledge to address socio-economic challenges and take care of users' needs.
- Position the RI in the local, national and international environment; identify regional research priorities and set consistent strategies.
- Identify and negotiate with potential funders; identify new funding tools e.g. private-public partnerships, special projects, commercial funding, fee for service, consultancy.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

The European Commission describes the main objectives of RIs and these represent OS outcomes provided by the RI professionals:

- OS practices are generalised, and fragmentation of the research ecosystem is reduced.
- Duplication of effort is avoided.

- Research outputs sharing is facilitated and supported.
- Open, usable and accessible research data and publications are produced.
- Innovation and research projects are boosted.
- Cross-disciplinarity and cooperation with industry is facilitated.

Further information

Contributors: Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Elena Sokolova, Angus Whyte

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#); [Conduct research across disciplines](#); [Develop professional network with researchers and scientists](#); [Draft scientific or academic papers and technical documentation](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Manage open publications](#); [Manage personal professional development](#); [Manage research data](#); [Negotiate compromises](#); [Operate open source software](#); [Perform project management](#); [Promote open innovation in research](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Adapt to change](#); [Address an audience](#); [Advise others](#); [Assume responsibility](#); [Build networks](#); [Demonstrate curiosity](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Manage financial and material resources](#); [Manage time](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Motivate others](#); [Organise information, objects and resources](#); [Plan](#); [Promote ideas, products, services](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Respect the diversity of cultural values and norms](#); [Show commitment](#); [Show confidence](#); [Show initiative](#); [Think analytically](#); [Think holistically](#); [Think innovatively](#); [Think quickly](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Work in teams](#).

ResearchComp: Apply research ethics and integrity principles; Ensure well-being at work; Interact professionally; Manage intellectual property rights; Mobilise resources.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Data costs management](#); [Data governance](#); [Data policy](#); [Knowledge to contextualise fair principles to domain](#); [Meeting/conference organisation](#); [Research integrity, attribution, impact awareness](#); [Selecting appropriate data handling methods](#); [Strategic/long-term planning](#); [Training in open and fair methods](#).

CSCCE: [Advancement, growth and sustainability](#); [Advocacy](#); [Business modeling](#); [Change management](#); [Collaboration](#); [Community governance](#); [Knowledge brokering](#); [Landscape analysis](#); [Meeting facilitation](#); [Moderation, mediation and intervention](#); [Networking](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Outreach](#); [Proposal development](#); [Strategy development](#).

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Scholarly Communications Professional

V0.5 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	10/06/2023	Initial content	Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou
0.2	28/06/2023	Reviewed content	Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou
0.3	10/07/2023	Review	Angus Whyte
0.4	19/11/2024	Conversion to a new template	Elena Sokolova
0.5	30/04/2025	Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

According to UNESCO, “Scholarly communication is the process of sharing, disseminating and publishing research findings of academics and researchers so that the generated academic contents are made available to the global academic communities”³. The Minimum Viable Skillset for Scholarly Communication Professionals describes the Open Science and Data Management skills required for those roles contributing to the creation, curation, and dissemination of scholarly outputs, with a particular attention to publications. Publications and scholarly outputs in general are not only the result of scientific activities, but a component of the open science ecosystem and therefore requiring the same OS and RDM skills as other OS products.

Scholarly Communication Professional

The Scholarly Communication Professional (SCP) deals with Scholarly Communication Artifacts, which entail, but are not limited to: articles, books, posts, annotations. SCPs engaged in Open Science ensure open access to the Scholarly Communication Artifacts, and more broadly their full integration into the OS environment. SCPs not only apply OS and RDM principles to the traditional and innovative forms of Scholarly Communication Artifacts, but they also address OS aspects beyond RDM best practices.

In that prospect, the SCP designs and/or implements OS policies and recommendations and applies methods and standards to ensure high-quality, accessible and reproducible research outputs.

Associated function titles: Publisher, Editor, Librarian.

Organisational context: Libraries, Research Performing Organizations (learned societies, universities, research centres), Scientific publishers, Research Infrastructures.

Essential Skills for this Role

³ <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000231938>.

- Expertise in data literacy both as a practitioner and a trainer.
- Knowledge of repositories and aggregator types, scope, and requirements.
- Knowledge of open publication models (green, gold, diamond).
- Ability to generate and understand bibliometrics, altmetrics, and usage metrics.
- Ability to apply FAIR principles to a variety of scholarly outputs, including expertise in persistent identification of contents, standard metadata generation and storage, and good knowledge of discipline-specific output types and standards.
- Knowledge about Linked Open Data and semantic interoperability.
- Knowledge about legal aspects related to IP/copyright/privacy, as well as data protection for sensitive data and information. Includes the ability to balance data protection requirements with open science/FAIR principles.
- Knowledge and ability to apply Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and the CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles.
- Ability to design, organize, and manage physical and digital trainings and events.

Soft/ transversal skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Team management and project management, for results-oriented planning and organisation.
- Stakeholder engagement and networking to translate and bridge needs.
- Creativity, curiosity and openness with a willingness to learn.
- Critical and analytical thinking.
- Conflict management and mediation, with a patient, empathic approach.

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Maintains and/or uses a publishing platform or a repository providing interoperable contents.
- Guides and supports users in disseminating standardized and FAIRified scholarly communication artifacts.
- Guides and supports users in enhancing their data literacy skills and working effectively with various types of data.
- Negotiates with publishers for open access publishing.
- Curates and enriches the data to ensure semantic and technical interoperability with a range of aggregators' specifications.
- Uses tools and follows procedures to achieve sustainability of published resources.
- Ensures compliance of published output with ethical and legal recommendations.
- Organises and monitors processes of content creation, review and dissemination.

- Integrates the aspects of diversity, inclusiveness and integrity in the process of information sharing.
- Participates and contributes to trans-professional networks including librarians, publishers, IT experts, legal experts, etc.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

The SCP manages Scholarly Communication Artifacts as research data, following OS and RDM principles, including the FAIR principles, both for the contents (e.g. using interoperable standard structured formats), and for their metadata (e.g., using PIDs and standard metadata schemas). The SCP ensures this way that Scholarly Communication Artifacts are not only disseminated as research results but made available as reusable research data.

LIBER (Association of European Research Libraries) identifies the following contributions to OS proper to librarians that also characterize any SCP's activity:

- Scholarly Communication Artifacts are accessible as research data, with relevant metrics, following OS and RDM principles.

Research integrity is enhanced by applying FAIR principles both to artifact contents e.g. using interoperable standard structured formats, and to their metadata e.g. using PIDs and standard metadata schemas.

Further information

Contributors: Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Elena Sokolova, Angus Whyte

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Develop professional network with researchers and scientists](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Manage open publications](#); [Manage research data](#); [Operate open-source software](#); [Perform project management](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Teach in academic or vocational contexts](#); [Think abstractly](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Advise others](#); [Apply basic programming skills](#); [Apply digital security measures](#); [Apply knowledge of science, technology and engineering](#); [Build networks](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Demonstrate willingness to learn](#); [Instruct others](#); [Manage quality](#); [Manage time](#); [Organize information, objects and resources](#); [Plan](#); [Promote ideas, products, services](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Respect the diversity of cultural values and norms](#); [Show empathy](#); [Show initiative](#); [Solve problems](#); [Think analytically](#); [Think creatively](#); [Think critically](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Work in teams](#).

ResearchComp: Abstract thinking; Interact professionally; Mobilise resources; Negotiate; Promote the transfer of knowledge.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Community building](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Data archiving](#); [Data categorisation](#); [Data curation](#); [Data governance](#); [Data policy](#); [Data quality assessment & review](#); [Digital archiving](#); [Evaluating repositories for data deposit/sharing](#); [Information security](#); [Knowledge to contextualize FAIR principles to domain](#); [Meeting/conference organization](#); [Mentoring on open and FAIR methods](#); [Metadata creation](#); [Metadata exposure](#); [Preservation](#); [Privacy governance](#); [Training in open and FAIR methods](#); [User acceptance testing](#).

CSCCE: [Advocacy](#); [Collaboration](#); [Community governance](#); [Consultation and listening](#); [Cultural competence](#); [Engagement](#); [Event planning](#); [Knowledge brokering](#); [Landscape analysis](#); [Media production](#); [Meeting facilitation](#); [Moderation, mediation and intervention](#); [Networking](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Outreach](#); [Record-keeping](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Teaching and training](#).

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Student – Masters Level

V0.5 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1		Initial content	Dominique Green, Saba Sharma, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia
0.2		Draft for internal review	As above and Benjamin Derksen, Lorna Wildgaard, Bernd Saurugger, Paula Martinez Lavanchy, Carolin Leister, Luca Schirru
0.3	10/10/2024	Revised to update the MVS layout	Dominique Green
0.4	12/12/2024	Revised to add Open Science Skills terms	Dominique Green
0.5	17/06/2025	Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Master's students is one of two MVS for students (the other for undergraduate students). As Master's level education is more specialised and focused than the undergraduate level this MVS considers the skills and competencies in Open Science (OS) needed for more focused study, incorporating OS into their project workflows. This is a generic profile for students in postgraduate education.

For information related to basic skills for researchers, see the MVS designed specifically for early career researchers, which addresses the minimum skills and competencies needed for PhD student and post-doctoral researchers.

It is recognised that Open Science skills should be immersed within formal education at its earliest stages. By engaging with Open Science practices and acquiring relevant knowledge of OS early in their careers, the benefits of these practices can be recognised, even if their careers are not in academia.

Master's student

Organisational context:

- Research Performing Organizations

Essential Skills for this Role

- Ability to analyse OS and FAIR concepts and ideas in the respective field of study. Where relevant, includes knowledge of ways to share and produce FAIR research data, code and

software, and of how to use data repositories.

- Intermediate digital research skills, data management, data communication. Includes demonstrating an understanding of the research life cycle, including planning, design, analysis, publication, and dissemination. Includes the ability to organise project workflow using file folders, document naming conventions, version control, cloud storage (etc.).
- Ability to obtain open science knowledge and apply FAIR principles, including relevant discipline or domain-specific information. Includes performing literature and data searches efficiently: finding and reusing open scientific papers, as well as finding, understanding, (re)using, and analysing the appropriate data types and formats for assignments.
- Open publication literacy skills, including knowledge of how to navigate open access sources and open access publication models applied to OA repositories.
- Basic understanding of the relevant legal issues related to Open Science practices, including Intellectual Property Rights, copyright-related issues like Open Access, Open Licensing, using and citing third-parties works. Also includes Non-Personal Data e.g., being aware of rules on the use of "research data".
- Knowledge of how to apply data protection requirements together with Open Science/FAIR principles. Includes Personal Data Protection and Governance e.g., using Personal Data under the current legal framework, and following Data Protection policies.
- General understanding of ethical principles e.g. transparency, diversity and accountability; and best practices e.g. avoiding bias in data processing when using data-driven technologies. Includes ability to relate these principles to their field of expertise, by applying the general ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct, e.g. the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

Soft/ transversal skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Collaboration skills, ability to engage in teamwork.
- Assignment and/or dissertation management.
- Organizational skills, including goal setting, time management, and prioritizing.
- Verbal communication and interpersonal skills.
- Written communication.
- Problem solving.
- Critical thinking.
- Presentation skills.

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Engages with OS outputs, and contributes to data literacy activities that improve their understanding of the concepts and principles of Open Science, including:
- Interpreting and critically evaluating data.
- Finding, selecting, accessing, and creating data sets.
- Ethically using and citing data.
- Understanding basic data types and formats.
- Communicating data with visualizations.
- Understanding how data is collected.
- Manipulating data from different sources, formats, and structures.
- Understanding how to store and share data.
- Understanding why it is important to manage data.
- Plans, organises, and manages assignments related to dissertations. Specific activities related to OS include:
- Using a data management plan to describe efforts to make research reproducible, including providing descriptions of the data via metadata, research procedures and analyses.
- Writing manuscripts and/or dissertations transparently, sharing hypotheses and justifying decisions, and sharing methodologies.
- Sharing any data used for projects, making the data available for researchers.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

Non-research graduate students contribute to the following Open Science outcomes:

- The adoption and practice of OS and FAIR principles and methods.
- Increasing transparency and knowledge sharing in research processes.
- Increasing knowledge and awareness of digital literacy.

Further information

Contributors: Dominique Green, Saba Sharma, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia, Luca Schirru, Angus Whyte, Paula Martinez Lavanchy, Carolin Leister, Bernd Sarugger.

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. Terms are selected to add further information and to aid discovery of this MVS (an extended list is added at the foot of this document). Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration](#)

and Community Engagement.

ESCO Research Skills: Perform project management; Manage research data; Synthesize research publications; Manage open publications; Manage findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable data; Operate open source software; Manage intellectual property rights; Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities.

ESCO Transversal Skills: Plan, conduct web searches; apply knowledge of science, technology, and engineering; Work in teams; address an audience; Moderate a discussion; Report facts; Use communication and collaboration software; Manage time; Organise information, objects, and resources; Solve problems; Critically evaluate information and its sources; Think critically; Show initiative; Assume responsibility; Show confidence.

ResearchComp: Manage research data; Apply research ethics and integrity principles; Problem solving; Creativity.

Terms4FAIRskills: Data transformation; Data validation and cleaning; Open access publishing; Data access risk assessment and mitigation; Ethical application of patents, licenses; Research governance; Data policy.

CSCCE: Data analysis; Data visualization; Speaking and presenting; Time management.

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Student – Undergraduate level

V0.6 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1		Initial content	Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Dominique Green, Saba Sharma, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, , Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia
0.2		Draft for discussion	As above + comments from Paula Martinez, Lorna Wildgaard, Carolin Leister, Benjamin Derksen, Bernd Saurugger
0.3		Draft v3 for internal review	As above
0.4	11/10/2024	Updated MVS layout	Dominique Green
0.5	12/12/2024	Updated profile to include Open Science skills terms	Dominique Green
0.6	17/06/2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

It is recognized that Open Science skills should be immersed within formal education at its earliest stages. Undergraduates are potential future researchers and open science practitioners. By taking part in relevant open science training early, undergraduates become concerned citizens and better equipped to support open science.

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Undergraduates addresses the minimum competencies and skills needed by undergraduate students at the completion of their degree program in Open Science (OS). The MVS profile for undergraduates considers that undergraduate students do not typically undertake extensive research projects. However, there are opportunities for undergraduates to interact with data and software whilst working on assignments. Therefore, this MVS for undergraduate students is a general profile developed specifically in regard to data literacy knowledge, as it serves as basis for relevant OS activities and knowledge of the FAIR principles. For information related to basic skills for graduate students who are undertaking research activities, typically via dissertations and other assignments, see the MVS designed for Master's Students. For the basic skills and competencies needed for early career researchers, including postgraduate students (PhDs), please see the MVS for early career researchers.

Undergraduate students

Organisational context:

- Research Performing Organisations (Universities)

Essential Skills for this Role

- Understanding of why it is important for society that research and data is open and FAIR.
- Ability to identify open science and FAIR principles, including relevant discipline or domain-specific information.
- Foundational digital research skills, e.g. knowledge of the research life cycle; organizing and documenting.
- Understand basic concepts of intellectual property and copyright and its importance in scientific work.
- Ability to identify the principles of open licensing and the uses and implications of open licenses.
- Know what is meant by research impact. Know the different types of impact indicators and how they work.
- Understand the importance of research visibility and know different ways to increase the visibility of research.
- Ability to apply basic open science principles in the relevant parts of the research life cycle, such as:
 - Recognising reliable and trustworthy sources of data.
 - Evaluating the quality and reusability of data.
 - Recognising the different open access model for scientific publications.
 - Knowledge of how to share FAIR research data, code and software, including knowledge of how to use repositories.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Collaboration and interpersonal skills, being particularly able to engage in teamwork.
- Written and verbal communication
- Time management
- Problem solving
- Critical thinking

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Contributes to data literacy activities that improves their OS knowledge and skills, including:
 - Interpreting and critically evaluating data.
 - Finding, selecting, accessing, and creating data sets.
 - Ethically using, collecting and citing data.

- Understanding basic data types and formats.
- Communicating data with appropriate visualizations.
- Understanding how the data was collected.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

The undergraduate contributes to the following OS outcomes:

- Development of data literacy abilities.
- Acquisition of a baseline of generic foundational digital skills.
- Adoption, awareness and understanding of OS and FAIR principles.
- Adoption of responsible and ethical use of data.

Further information

Contributors: Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Saba Sharma, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Karolina Dostatnia, Luca Schirru, Dominique Green, Angus Whyte

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. Terms are selected to add further information and to aid discovery of this MVS (an extended list is added at the foot of this document). Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Synthesise research publications](#); [Manage open publications](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Manage findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable data](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Plan, Organise information, objects, and resources](#); [Conduct web searches](#); [Show commitment](#); [Work in teams](#); [Build team spirit](#); [Address an audience](#); [Report facts](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Manage time](#); [Critically evaluate information and its sources](#); [Apply knowledge of science, technology and engineering](#).

ResearchComp: Problem solving; Creativity.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Data sharing and publication](#); [Data quality assessment](#); [Open access publishing](#).

CSCCE: [Speaking and presenting](#).

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